

Origin	Entries (no.)	Genotypes (no.) with given disease rating ^a		
		R (1-5%)	I (6-25%)	S (>25 %)
CIAT, Colombia	198	126	38	34
EMBRAPA, Brazil	16	15	1	0
Indonesia	91	0	10	81
IRRI, Philippines	132	35	64	33
Total	437	176	113	148

Local checks:
C22 (S): 100% dead
Danau Laut Tawar (R): 3, 4 (25%)

^a Disease severities evaluated according to disease damage index keys to estimate damage caused by major diseases of upland rice. R = resistant, I = intermediate, S = susceptible.

Pest resistance — insects

Evaluation of rice cultivars for resistance to leafhopper (LF)

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We screened 81 rice cultivars from the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, for LF resistance 1986-87.

Entries were direct seeded in 4 - × 1.05-m plots with two replications. Recommended agronomic practices were followed.

LF infestation was heavy 70 d after sowing, when the crop was in the booting to flowering stage. Susceptible check Brown gora had 90% infestation. Damaged and undamaged leaves of each test entry were counted in 1 m² of each replication, and averages calculated. Percentage damaged leaves was converted into 0-9 point scale:

$$\text{Scale} = \frac{\% \text{ damaged leaves in test cultivar}}{\% \text{ damaged leaves in susceptible check}}$$

In 1986, RP1714-111-7-3-2 and OR811-2 had no LF damage. In 1987, RD2599-150-18-8-5 and RAU156-56 had no damage.

Reactions of most cultivars changed in 1987. RP1714-111-7-3-2 and OR811-2, which had 0 damage in 1986, were evaluated at 3 in 1987.

Cultivars that scored 0, 1, and 3 both years could be treated as resistant and used in a crossing program (see table). ■

Cultivars that scored 0-3 for LF resistance. Ranchi, India, 1986 and 1987.

Score	Cultivars
	<i>1986</i>
0	RP1714-111-7-3-2, OR811-2
1	RP2217-71-73-14, RP2525-19-124, RP1888-132-24-11-8, RP2522-16-14-80, NDR119, UPR83-28, UPR83-20, NDK224, NDR222, BG367-4, and CN747-1-4
3	RP2415-203-5-1-2, RP2263-934-592-5, RP2235-35-40-50, RTN500, RP2423-5-77-16, TNAU301790, Akashi, TNAU81804, NRL502, TNAU83134, TNAU83108, NDR312-1, NR571-1, MAUSEL 10, RP2601-24-36-138, Pusa 510, JR35, OR811-10, RP2599-150-18-8-5, ADT85001, RAU151-56
	<i>1987</i>
0	RP2599-150-188-8-5, RAU151-56
1	OR811-10, ADT85001, RP2522-16-14-80, NDR119, UPR83-28, TNAU83108
3	RP1714-111-7-3-2, OR811-2, RP2217-71-73-14, RP2525-19-124, RP1888-132-24-11-8, UPR83-20, NDR224, NDR222, BG367-4, CN747-1-4, RP2415-203-5-1-2, RP2263-934-592-5, RTN500, RP2423-5-77-16, Akashi, Pusa 510, RAU4071-51-13, RAU4045-2A.

Stress tolerance — excess water

Inheritance of submergence tolerance in rice

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We traced inheritance of submergence tolerance in six submergence-tolerant advanced lines crossed with susceptible IR11288-B-B-69-1. Seeds of the parents, F₁, and F₂ were sown in 5- × 5-cm plastic pots and placed in galvanized iron trays in the glasshouse. Seedlings were pulled 35 d after sowing and tillers separated to test submergence tolerance. At 10 d after separation, trays containing potted tillers were put in a tank inside the greenhouse and the plants submerged to 90 cm for 12 d. Recovery was measured 7 d after submergence.

Submergence tolerance of the F₁ and F₂ was calculated by dividing their survival by the survival percentage of the tolerant parent.

Survival in the F₁ of four crosses tended toward the tolerant parent; survival in two crosses was very poor (see table). This implies that dominance of submergence tolerance varies.

Although survival of the F₁ of BKNFR76106-16-0-1/IR11288 was very poor, the F₂ showed tolerance (which was expected). The reason for the discrepancy in the F₁ is not clear.

Survival was higher in crosses involving strongly submergence-tolerant parents that derive their tolerance from FR13A or Kurkaruppan (BKNFR76106-13-2 and IR29012-4-1-3 from FR13A and IR31406-333-1 from Kurkaruppan). Survival was lower in the crosses involving moderately tolerant parents IR21567-16-2-2 and IR8234-OT-9-2 (they presumably obtained their genes for tolerance from moderately tolerant KLG6986 and Nam Sagui 19).